

Question raised by requestor

Is there scientific knowledge regarding the impact of nearby wind turbines on cattle welfare? If this is the case, is there a distance recommended between the farms and the wind turbines to avoid welfare consequences? Can bovine animals get used to the effects of wind turbines (noise, shadow, etc.)?

Answer

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* received the question on 7 June 2024. The answers regarding wind turbines effects on bovine was sent 17 October 2024. Scientific knowledge relating directly to bovine and wind turbines is lacking. Due to this, recommendations on appropriate distances are unknown. This answer describes legislation and research on wind turbines, noise and habituation.

Regulation surrounding noise and electricity

Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes does not refer to sound exposure for animals (1). Annex 'Animals not kept in buildings' Article 12 states that "*animals not kept in buildings shall where necessary and possible be given protection from adverse weather conditions, predators and risks to their health.*" This could potentially include sound exposure if it negatively impacts animal health. For settlements or residential areas, Member States have their own regulations and recommendations on the setback distance to wind turbines, which range from 120–1250 m (2).

Wind turbines effect on animals

While there is limited information on wind turbines and their effects on domesticated bovines, there is information on other species. In wild animals, wind turbines have been known to alter their behaviour. Many wildlife species have been investigated in respect to wind turbines including bats, birds, and large mammals, such as roe deer and reindeer. Ungulates change their habitat selection or land use based on proximity to wind farms (3, 4). Semi-domesticated reindeer also avoid habitats where wind turbines are visible and in operation compared to when they were being built (5). This suggests that there is some aspect that is unpleasant to experience near the turbines and given the choice animals will avoid the area. In addition, cortisol levels in roe deer faecal samples are higher near large wind farms, which may be indicative of increased stress (3). The larger farms consisted of more than 18 turbines, and therefore the increased land use due to the number of turbines and reduced areas of refuge may be more important than the distance to the wind turbine (3). The size of the wind farm and additional infrastructure (i.e., cable networks and buildings) can also disrupt animals during the building phase (6). An important distinction to make is that domesticated cattle are typically fenced and cannot move away from the disturbing noise; however, domesticated animals are more likely to adapt to the noise (6).

In terms of bovines, a case study of two cattle farms in France determined that the wind farms, which were located between 700 and 1500 m away, were unlikely to be responsible for the health issues on the respective farms (7). However, the researchers could not rule out the effects of the wind farms (7).

Sound

Noise is an unwanted chronic or intermittent sound, which is related to frequency (Hz) and intensity (dB). Noise can cause discomfort to animals and should be monitored. Cattle can hear sounds with frequencies between 23–35000 Hz (8). Sensitivity to frequency depends on the genetics and breed of the cattle and beef breeds are less sensitive to frequency than dairy breeds (9). Noise that is sudden and high pitched may frighten an animal (8). Wind turbines produce various sounds, the common 'whooshing' sound is typically higher than 100 Hz, while low frequency sounds (between 20–100 Hz) are also produced (10). The highest known frequency from a wind turbine is 770–2000 Hz, which is still considered mid-pitch (10).

Sound intensity levels have varying results. Levels higher than 70 dB are likely to impact animal welfare, but intensity levels between 90–100 dB cause discomfort and intensity levels higher than 110 dB cause ear damage in cattle (8,9). On farms, there are many sounds, from animals, humans, equipment and machinery. Sound intensity of fans in sheds range between 55–67 dB, when properly assembled and maintained (8). The average equivalent intensity for multiple

milking parlours (i.e., rotary, side-by-side, herringbone, tandem, and group automatic milking systems) ranged from 60.7–69.5 dB (11). Based on the recommended settlement distance from wind turbines, the intensity of the sound should be no more than 45 dB (2), less than other sounds experienced by cattle on farms and below the maximum recommended sound levels.

Shadows and sudden movements

In relation to 'shadow flicker' caused by the rotating blades of wind turbines, there is a lack of empirical evidence to determine whether they have an impact on bovine welfare. Noise and visual disturbance from wind turbines are considered to have a weak effect on livestock (6).

Habituation

Habituation to sound between 60–90 dB is possible, however, sounds exceeding this level may cause adverse effects to physiology and behaviour (8). Domesticated animals are more likely to adapt and become habituated to certain sound and visual cues compared to wild animals, especially if they are predictable, prolonged and repeated (6). In a study conducted in Australia on noise habituation, heifers were put through a raceway 3 times a day for 15 consecutive days (12). Half of the heifers had pre-recorded milking facility noise (85 dB) introduced to the raceway on days 5–10. The heifers exposed to noise, moved faster through the raceway each day and showed increased heart rates on the first day of noise exposure (day 5). There was no difference in latency to enter the raceway, cortisol concentrations or handling parameters. The authors suggested that the increased heart rate and speed were fear responses, and noted that after 12 exposures to the noise, habituation was evident (12). Horses can also be habituated to sound (80 dB) over consecutive exposures (13).

Habituation is more likely for domesticated animals compared to wildlife. In semi-domesticated, enclosed reindeer there was a variable response to a still wind turbine compared to a rotating wind turbine on the edge of the enclosure (14). Systematic behavioural changes have not been observed in animals near still or rotating turbines, indicating stress or flight responses are not triggered by wind turbines (14). Since the noise of a wind turbine does not indicate immediate risk to animals, habituation is anticipated (6).

Conclusion

There is a lack of research on the effect of wind turbines on the welfare of farmed animals such as cattle, however, studies on wildlife have demonstrated avoidance behaviour in areas with wind turbines. It is expected that domesticated species will not be harmed by the sound of wind turbines and will habituate. Member States have their own regulations and recommendations on the setback distance between residential settlements and wind turbines, which range from 120–1250 m (2). Further research is needed to understand the effect of wind turbines on domesticated animals and to establish guidelines on the distance between farms and wind turbines, with consideration for the size of the wind farm (number of turbines) and farmed species.

References

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